

Effective Performance Management System: Empirical Study from Saudi Arabia.

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Abstract

The goal of the paper is to find the characteristics which can lead to an effective performance management systems. The paper suggested a model with a set of characteristics in three critical intervals for the performance management process: when identifying performance objectives, when measuring performance, and when developing performance.

Keywords

Performance, Performance Management, Evaluation System

Introduction

Although applied by many, a high number of HR managers think that we are not getting that much benefit of Performance Management Systems (Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011), if not even harming the organization (Michal Biron, Elaine Farndale, Jaap Paauwe, 2011). However, if a PMS designed and implemented well, we can gain much clear jobs and goals, motivated and competent employees, and an overall enhancement of organizational effectiveness.

And here a question arises of what makes a PMS an effective one, and this is what I am trying to answer in this paper. But first, let us set what we mean by a Performance Management System (PMS). Performance management is a continuous process of identifying, measuring, and developing the performance of individuals and teams and aligning performance with the strategic goals of the organization (Aguinis, 2013). To manage performance, we use an open system called a Performance Management System. It is fundamental to note that the Performance Management System is not a Performance Appraisal System which is a system through which we describe employee's strengths and weaknesses, performance appraisal is only a part of performance management.

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To have an idea of what makes a PMS effective we first take a look at a review of literature followed by a model, methodology, discussion of the findings, limitations, and some suggestions for future research.

Literature Review

Even that till now we still don't have a sufficient understanding of the factors likely to enhance the effectiveness of performance management systems (Michal Biron, Elaine Farndale, Jaap Paauwe, 2011), *we can find suggested characteristics or qualities in the literature that helps in having an effective PMS*. Among them are those related to the identification of performance: (a) Strategic Alignment is one of the most important criteria, hence that any organization is meeting its goals through its individual employees' performance? (Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011) and (Aguinis, 2013) suggested the alignment of the PMS with strategic goals of the HR function which is in order aligned with the strategic goals of the organization. Others also suggested tight alignment between the PMS and the Management By Objectives system (Michael Beer, Robert Ruh, Javk A. Dawson, B. B. McCAA, Michael J. Kavanagh, 1978). Other criteria for a PMS to be effective is to (b) Motivate employees. (Angelo S. DeNisi, Robert D. Pritchard, 2006) suggest a model "that focuses on the choice of where individuals should expend their effort." (Aguinis, 2013) focused on the importance of (c) Employees Engagement by taking their input about how the performance should be measured. Other criteria to have a PMS that is (d) Culturally Congruent with the organization and country that is operating at (Aguinis, 2013; Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011). (Aguinis, 2013) Also mentioned the importance of having a clear, and detailed guidance about what is expected from the employees and how they can achieve what is expected.

Other criteria exist in the literature related to the measurement of performance: (a) Accuracy and consistency are the most characteristics to receive interest in the literature. In a review of the literature (Muhammad Zahid Iqbal, Saeed Akbar, Pawan Budhwar, 2014) found that the greater proportion of articles are focusing on having an accurate PMSs when measuring performance. Having consistent and standardized measurements is also of high importance (Aguinis, 2013). Another criterion is to have a sort of (b) Purposefulness in the system by using measures that are relevant and under the control of the employees (Muhammad Zahid Iqbal, Saeed Akbar, Pawan Budhwar, 2014; Aguinis, 2013). Also for a PMS to be effective, it must be (c) Thorough and Identifies between effective and ineffective performance, so all employees and job responsibilities should be evaluated, at all the review period, delivering both positive and negative feedback, and the various levels of performance should be differentiated based on that (Aguinis, 2013). He also advice having a sort of (d) Practicality in the system, especially in the evaluation forms. There is no perfect system so for a PMS to be effective it must be (e) Correctible, there must be a formal mechanism to make corrections (Aguinis, 2013).

There also criteria related to the developmental aspect of PMSs: (a) Openness is one of them (Aguinis, 2013). Evaluation and feedback must be provided frequently, performance review meetings should be a two-way communication process, standards should be clear, and communications should be factual, open, and honest. (b) Acceptability and Fairness (Muhammad Zahid Iqbal, Saeed Akbar, Pawan Budhwar,

2014; Aguinis, 2013) and (c) Ethicality (Aguinis, 2013) also received a high level of attention.

(Michael Beer, Robert Ruh, Javk A. Dawson, B. B. McCAA, Michael J. Kavanagh, 1978) mentioned that to develop performance, employees must be (d) Open to Influence and ready to receive constructive feedback. At the same time, supervisors should be (e) Supportive (Michael Beer, Robert Ruh, Javk A. Dawson, B. B. McCAA, Michael J. Kavanagh, 1978).

Others saw that a PMS is effective when the organization is using certain practices or behaviors. Before the appraisal period, there are a set of practices recommended in the literature: (a) Having the senior management's support by conceding the PMS as the mean in which the strategic and tactical organizational objectives are pursued helps in budgeting, clarity of objectives, and a positive attitude toward the system (Deborah F. Boice, Brian H. Kleiner, 1997). Dealing with performance management as other functions need's a special set of competencies. (b) Training sessions must be provided to all employees, booth who will be appraising or appraised. This can help in the acceptance of the system, minimize rating errors, better identification of high performers, and better identification of developmental needs (Michal Biron, Elaine Farndale, Jaap Paauwe, 2011; Deborah F. Boice, Brian H. Kleiner, 1997; Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011; Chen, Kevin Baird Herbert, Schoch Qi James, 2012). To ensure clarity we need to b. Communicate Clear and Measurable objectives periodically to address the situation of the organization and where it is going and what is the role of every individual in all of that. Also, we need to ensure that employees have SMART (an acronym for specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely) goals to help guide their performance (Michal Biron, Elaine Farndale, Jaap Paauwe, 2011; Deborah F. Boice, Brian H. Kleiner, 1997; Rao, 2007). PMS should be (c) Integrated with the organizational strategy and other HR functions. Input must be taken from business strategy, and the PMS output must contribute to the formulation of the business strategy. Also, PMSs must receive input and provide output to the HR function (Rao, 2007; Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011). (d) Having employees contribute to the decision of what will be measured and how, increases the acceptance and meaningfulness of the PMS (Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011).

For the system to get results, it must be meaningful and purposeful for employees. If employees perceived the PMS as just another administrative task that we finish and go back to real tasks the system will be of no use. So, Periodic Signals should be provided to ensure that employees at all levels are getting why we have chosen to use the system and how to use it (Deborah F. Boice, Brian H. Kleiner, 1997; Rao, 2007).

There are a set of recommended practices required at the evaluating period: If we are thinking of performance conversations only as the formal meetings usually near the appraisal period, we might be missing the core of a PMS. It is the (a) Day to Day Communications about what is to be done, how an employee is doing it, and how he or she can improve his or her competency to do it better. Day to day communication rather than once in a year or a six months can increase clarity, motivation, and sense to the system (Elaine D. Pulakos, 2011). Usually referred to as 360-degree feedback, (b) Multisource feedback helps in increasing the accuracy and acceptance when measuring performance. Rather than assigning supervisors only to rate performance, ratings can be taken by subordinates, coworkers, customers, and the employees themselves (Deborah F.

Boice, Brian H. Kleiner, 1997; Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011). (c) Accurate record keeping of individual strengths and weaknesses can help feeding imputation to training and development, career planning, skills inventory, reward, and other HR interventions (Deborah F. Boice, Brian H. Kleiner, 1997).

Also at the end of the appraisal period, a set of recommendation can be founded in the literature: When we appraise performance we are not judging if a person is good or bad, rather we are interested in (a) Finding Measurable destructive behaviors to eliminate and constructive behaviors to reinforce (Rao, 2007). If results are accurate reward, training, separation, and (b) Administrative Decisions can be enforced and justified by the appraisal results (Rao, 2007; Victor Y. Haines III, Sylvie St-Onge, 2011). Mainly (c) Review Meetings should be separated to ensure attention for every aspect, especially the discussion of rewards and career development (Aguinis, 2013). We are interested in rewarding behaviors that are helping us in achieving our objectives, so by providing (d) Contingent pay plans that enforce high performance we can contribute in retaining top performers (Herman Aguinis, Ryan K. Gottfredson, Harry Joo, 2012; Rao, 2007; Chen, Kevin Baird Herbert Schoch Qi (James), 2012). Appraising performance is only a part of managing performance. Focusing on rating employees only provides no benefit other than trolling employees. The goal is to measure to take some actions, mainly to develop. We need to (e) Focus on Development rather than measurement (Rao, 2007; Angelo S. DeNisi, Robert D. Pritchard, 2006). An employee now knows what his or her weaknesses are, can make use of (f) Individualized Developmental Plans to overcome them. Developmental objectives can be mutually decided upon between employees and managers at the beginning of the appraisal period. Then particular actions can be assigned to tackle them, and at the end of the appraisal period progress can be measured (Herman Aguinis, Ryan K. Gottfredson, Harry Joo, 2012).

Research Model

Adapted from previous criteria discussed in the literature review, this is a model that describes a set of characteristics that might lead to an effective PMS. Instead of only focusing on certain aspects of the system such as performance measurement, this model tries to give a holistic view of the system. We can break down main activities executed in the PMS into three main intervals identifying performance objectives, measuring performance, and developing performance. In the first interval, we set what the performance targets are and how we will achieve them. In the second interval, we measure how well we are achieving these targets. In the third interval, we correct what we did wrong and reinforce what we did well. When we do these three activities well we are more likely to have an effective PMS, that is a PMS where continually performance targets are achieved, exceeded, and competencies are being developed. Now after we have sat the general structure of the model, we can take a deeper look at what qualities or characteristics (independent variables) required when executing these three intervals which can lead to the outcomes (dependent variables) of an effective PMS.

There are thirteen independent variables distributed among the main intervals. Some of these independent variables have two or more dimensions. Although meaningfulness, ethicality, acceptability and fairness, and openness are required mostly at certain intervals they should apply for the total system.

Figure 1- Conceptual model of relationships among the characteristics of effective performance management system

When identifying performance objectives, first needed quality is specificity. Specificity is a quality of a system where objectives and how to reach them are clearly communicated in a detailed manner. Second is meaningfulness, which is a quality where employees perceive the system as important and relevant to their day to day tasks. Third is strategic alignment, which is a quality of system where individual performance targets contribute toward achieving the department objectives which are based on the organizational objectives. Fourth, Inclusiveness is a quality of a system where employees are included in the process of setting what to be measured and how.

When measuring performance, first needed quality is validity. Validity is quality in which the system is measuring what should be measured. There are two dimensions in this variable. One is related the measures being covering all critical performance facets (Validity1), another means that the measures do not include factors outside the control of the employees (Validity2).

Second is reliability, which is a quality which means that the measures are consistent and free of error. The third is thoroughness, which means that all employees and performance targets are evaluated on the entire evaluation period. There are two dimensions in this variable. One is related to have evaluations covering the entire review period (Thoroughness1), another is a dimension related to feedback being provided about both positive and negative performance (Thoroughness2). Fourth is practicality, which means that the system is easy to use and its benefits outweigh its costs. There are two

dimensions in this variable. One means that the system is easy to use (Practicality1), and another means that the benefits of the system outweigh its costs (Practicality2). Fifth is ethicality, which means that the system complies with ethical standards. There are two dimensions in this variable. One means that the supervisors suppress their self-interest in providing evaluations (Ethicality1), another means that the supervisors evaluate performance dimensions only for which they have sufficient information (Ethicality2). Sixth is Correctability, which is a quality of a system where appraisals can appeal against their ratings can be made through the feedback of the users of the system. Seventh is identification of effective and ineffective performance, which means that the system differentiates between effective and ineffective behaviors and results, also differentiates between poor and high performers.

When developing performance, first needed quality is acceptability and fairness which is the level of employees perceived distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informational justice. There are four dimensions of this variable. The first dimension means that the employees perceive the performance evaluation and rewards received relative to the work performed as fair (distributive justice). The second dimension means that the employees perceive the procedures used to determine the ratings and subsequent rewards as fair (procedural justice). The third dimension means that the employees perceive the way they are treated in the course of designing and implementing the system as fair (interpersonal justice). The fourth dimension means that the employees perceive the information and explanations they receive as part of the performance management system as fair (informational justice). Second is openness, which is a quality of a system in which evaluation and feedback are being provided frequently, performance review meetings are a two-way communication process, standards are clear, and communications are factual, open, and honest. There are two dimensions in this variable. One means that appraisal meeting is a two-way communication process (Openness1), another means that standards are clear and communicated on an ongoing basis (Openness2).

There are three dependent variables in the model. First is performance completion, which means that the performance targets are being reached. Second is performance differentiation, which is the employee performance exceeds the targets. The third is performance development, which is the PMS is enhancing the competence of employees.

Methodology

To find whether these characteristics (independent variables) suggested in the model leads to Performance Management System effectiveness, I used quantitative exploratory research with a deductive approach. Data were collected using a survey. The population consists of employees working in Saudi Arabia. A questionnaire including 26 items was randomly distributed through Google forms, and 36 responses have been received. Reliability analysis have been done using Cronbach's Alpha, and the result was (0.945). Check (table1 Reliability analysis) in appendix A for more details. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20.

Findings and Discussion

All of the thirteen characteristics are associated with having an effective PMS. Starting with characteristics required when identifying performance objectives, all four characteristics (independent variables) showed a varying level of correlation with two or more outcomes of an effective PMS (dependent variables). Detailed correlation analysis statistics can be found in Table 2 in appendix A.

Specificity is correlated with performance completion, differentiation, and development. That is when objectives and how to reach them are clearly communicated, employees will be better able to reach and exceed their performance targets and enhance their competencies. At the beginning of the evaluation period, specific required behaviors and results must be clear for the employees. A worker on an assembly line must know what is expected of him or her regarding how to process (required behaviors) each unit, and how many units to be produced (required results). When employees sign that they understood or committed to achieving these behaviors and results, still that does not mean that these targets are clear. Continues signaling of these objectives, manuals, and in job training should be provided.

Meaningfulness is correlated with performance completion and development. Which means that when employees perceive the system as important and relevant to their day to day tasks, they will be able to reach their performance targets and develop their competencies. If employees view the system as something done by the organization every year to justify salary increment only, the system is way far from meeting its benefits. Instead, employees should view the system as the mean that helps them in facilitating day to day performance by continuously setting what to do and how, how we are doing it, and what will we gain in a result. The more the system is relevant to every employee the more it is meaningful.

Strategic Alignment is correlated with performance completion, differentiation, and development. That is when employees' actions are in sync with departmental and overall organizational objectives, performance targets will be reached and exceeded, and employees will be better able to enhance their competencies. Individual, departmental, and organizational objectives being aligned does not necessarily mean that the objectives are provided by top management and must be followed by departmental and personal objectives. Instead, there should be a level of interaction and adjustments between those three levels when setting objectives to ensure that they are in tune in order to enhance the overall effectiveness and adaptation of the organization.

Inclusiveness is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. Which means that when employees are included in setting what to be measured and how, they will be more likely to reach and exceed their performance targets. Including employees in setting what to be measured and how can help in increasing commitment, meaningfulness, and buy-in for the system.

All seven characteristics (independent variables) required when measuring performance showed a varying level of correlation with two or more outcomes of an effective PMS (dependent variables) except for validity (1). Detailed correlation analysis statistics can be found in Table 3 in appendix A.

Validity (1) didn't show any relation with any dimension of PMS effectiveness. Validity (2) is correlated with both performance completion and differentiation. If measures do

not include factors outside the control of the employees' performance, targets can be reached and exceeded. It is important to note here that especially with jobs with a high level of uncertainty, deciding upon what measures to use can be tricky. A classic example of this is salespeople. Even if sales are low, it might be because of a current decrease in the economic growth. Moreover, even if sales are high, it might be because of environmental factors that led to an increase in demand. In such cases, the focus should be more on behavioral measures such as personal selling skills, instead of result based measures such as the amount of the sales.

Reliability is correlated with booth performance completion and differentiation. That is when measures are consistent, the system can help employees in reaching and exceeding performance targets. Even though it is very hard, the system should be in a way that whoever and whenever an employee is appraised, in the same evaluation period, measurement result must be similar.

Figure 2- Correlations among first interval independent variables and the dependent variables (arrows show where there is correlation)

Thoroughness (1) and Thoroughness (2) is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. When evaluations cover the entire evaluation period and feedback is provided about both positive and negative behaviors, performance targets can be reached and exceeded. Appraising covers all the evaluation period, filling the appraisal form is at the end of the evaluation period. Although this is very simple, a high number of appraisers focuses only at or near the end of the evaluation period. Also, especially at the performance review meetings, the discussion should cover both what the employee did well and what he or she did poorly.

Practicality (1) is correlated with performance completion, differentiation, and development. That is the system is easy to use, performance targets can be reached and exceeded, and competencies can be developed. Practicality (2) is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. Which means that when employees think that the benefits of the system outweigh the costs, performance targets can be reached and exceeded. Designing a form that is comprehensive yet simple is a tough task. However, the more we balance these two aspects, the more we can enhance the effectiveness of the system.

Ethicality (1) and Ethicality (2) is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. When supervisors suppress their self-interest in providing evaluations and evaluate performance dimensions only for which they have sufficient information, performance targets can be reached and exceeded. The system must comply with ethical standards, with zero tolerance for any violations.

Correctability is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. Which means that when adjustment can be made through the feedback of the system's users, performance targets can be reached and exceeded. Performance Management System is an open system, which means that the system feeds forward to its environment and receive feedback from it. So there must be formal mechanisms in which employees make corrections and adjustments in the system.

Identification of effective and ineffective performance is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. Which means that when the system differentiates between effective and ineffective behaviors and results, the system can help employees reach and exceed performance targets. If an employee is performing well, yet he or she gets a similar evaluation as others with poor performance, the system will contribute to damaging relationships and employee burnout.

Figure 3- Correlations between second interval independent variables and the dependent variables (arrows show where there is correlation)

The two characteristics (independent variables) required when developing performance showed a varying level of correlation with two or more outcomes of an effective PMS (dependent variables). Detailed correlation analysis statistics can be found in Table 4 in appendix A.

Acceptability and fairness (distributive justice) is correlated with performance completion, differentiation, and development. Which means that when employees perceive the performance evaluation and rewards received relative to the work performed as fair, performance targets can be reached, exceeded, and competencies can be developed. Acceptability and fairness (procedural justice) is booth correlated with performance completion and differentiation. Which means that when employees perceive the procedures used to determine the ratings and subsequent rewards as fair, they will be better able to reach and exceed performance targets. Acceptability and fairness (interpersonal justice) is correlated with performance completion and differentiation. Which means that when employees perceive the way they are treated in the course of designing and implementing the system as fair, performance targets can be reached and exceeded. Acceptability and fairness (informational justice) is correlated with performance completion and differentiation.

Which means that when employees perceive the information and explanations they receive as part of the performance management system as fair, performance targets can be reached and exceeded, also competencies can be developed.

Openness (1) and Openness (2) is correlated with performance completion, differentiation, and development. That is when appraisal meeting is a two-way communication process, and standards are clear and communicated on an ongoing basis, performance targets can be reached and exceeded, and competencies can be developed.

Figure 4- Correlations between third interval independent variables and the dependent variables (arrows show where there is correlation)

Limitations and Future Research

One of the limitations of this paper is that the sample size is small and might not be a good representative of the population. Also due to the limitation of the survey method, data might be affected by biases. Especially for items measuring performance effectiveness, most respondents rated them self as good performers, which might be just an exaggeration. To overcome this problem, future research can use an experiment with a control group instead of a survey to collect data. Using the provided model we can build on by finding what practices that can lead to these required characteristics.

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Appendix A (Tables)

Table 1- Reliability score

Cronbach's Alpha		N of Items		
.945		26		
Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Strategic Alignment	87.8056	337.075	.381	.946
Thoroughness1	87.6944	331.990	.612	.943
Thoroughness2	87.7500	321.393	.671	.942
Practicality1	88.0000	331.257	.576	.943
Practicality2	88.2222	328.463	.608	.943
Meaningfulness	87.8611	327.552	.560	.944
Specificity	87.9444	323.597	.663	.942
Identification of effective and ineffective performance	88.0833	323.793	.786	.941
Reliability	88.7222	319.292	.683	.942
Validity1	88.0833	329.507	.647	.943
Validity2	88.0556	330.225	.547	.944
Acceptability and fairness distributive justice	88.0556	326.454	.626	.943
Acceptability and fairness procedural	88.1389	328.352	.708	.942
Acceptability and fairness interpersonal	88.1944	320.390	.792	.941
Acceptability and fairness informational	88.2500	321.450	.775	.941
Inclusiveness	88.3611	325.380	.637	.943
Openness1	88.0833	318.536	.717	.942
Openness2	87.8611	320.523	.827	.940
Correctability	88.1667	318.886	.744	.941
Ethicality1	87.9722	325.113	.656	.942
Ethicality2	87.8889	325.816	.625	.943
Performance (completion)	87.3611	337.952	.512	.944
Performance (differentiation)	87.4444	337.911	.500	.944
performance development	87.4722	343.742	.254	.947

Table 2- Correlation analysis of the characteristics required when identifying performance objectives and the outcomes of an effective PMS

Correlations				
		Performance completion	Performance differentiation	Performance development
Specificity	Pearson Correlation	.235	.269	.328
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.168	.112	.051
	N	36	36	36
Meaningfulness	Pearson Correlation	.278	.159	.235
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.100	.354	.167
	N	36	36	36
Strategic Alignment	Pearson Correlation	.298	.231	.330*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.078	.176	.050
	N	36	36	36
Inclusiveness	Pearson Correlation	.219	.248	.025
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.200	.145	.885
	N	36	36	36
<i>Correlation is significant at the 0.01**</i>				
<i>Correlation is significant at the 0.05*</i>				

Table 3- Correlation analysis of the characteristics required when measuring performance and the outcomes of an effective PMS

Correlations				
		Performance completion	Performance differentiation	Performance development
Validity1	Pearson Correlation	.131	.130	.092
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.448	.449	.595
	N	36	36	36
Validity2	Pearson Correlation	.260	.287	.178
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.125	.089	.299
	N	36	36	36
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	.270	.267	-.046-

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.112	.115	.788
	N	36	36	36
Thoroughness1	Pearson Correlation	.342*	.274	.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	.106	.771
	N	36	36	36
Thoroughness2	Pearson Correlation	.440**	.305	.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	.071	.648
	N	36	36	36
Practicality1	Pearson Correlation	.247	.377*	.249
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.146	.023	.143
	N	36	36	36
Practicality2	Pearson Correlation	.403*	.324	.129
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	.054	.453
	N	36	36	36
Ethicality1	Pearson Correlation	.361*	.252	.082
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	.138	.636
	N	36	36	36
Ethicality2	Pearson Correlation	.263	.247	-.102-
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.121	.146	.552
	N	36	36	36
Correctability	Pearson Correlation	.403*	.441**	.006
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	.007	.972
	N	36	36	36
Identification of effective & ineffective performance	Pearson Correlation	.290	.285	.089
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.087	.092	.604
	N	36	36	36
<i>Correlation is significant at the 0.01**</i>				
<i>Correlation is significant at the 0.05*</i>				

Table 4- Correlation analysis of the characteristics required when developing performance and the outcomes of an effective PMS

Correlations				
		Performance completion	Performance differentiation	Performance development
Acceptability and fairness distributive	Pearson Correlation	.341*	.253	.222
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.042	.136	.194
	N	36	36	36
Acceptability and fairness procedural	Pearson Correlation	.176	.304	-.020-
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.304	.071	.909
	N	36	36	36
Acceptability and fairness interpersonal	Pearson Correlation	.360*	.459**	.198
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.031	.005	.246
	N	36	36	36
Acceptability and fairness informational	Pearson Correlation	.488**	.435**	.199
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.008	.243
	N	36	36	36
Openness1	Pearson Correlation	.278	.298	.216
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.101	.077	.206
	N	36	36	36
Openness2	Pearson Correlation	.346*	.450**	.342*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	.006	.041
	N	36	36	36
<i>Correlation is significant at the 0.01**</i>				
<i>Correlation is significant at the 0.05*</i>				